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Pragmatics Analysis of the Selected Kafi of Khawaja Ghulam Fareed

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Abstract

The study provides an in-depth analysis of the speaker's emotional trajectory, characterized by their tragic separation from a significant person and their profound relationship with the supernatural realm. The speaker conveys his willingness to persevere through adversity clearly and convincingly while enthusiastically praising the sacred and faultless character of the Divine home. It is characterized by a qualitative method, and its primary objective is to offer an explanatory explanation of the phenomena that are being investigated. The field of pragmatics is subjected to an in-depth investigation in this work, with an emphasis placed on fundamental aspects, including pragmatics, speech acts, hyperbole, metaphorical language, and assertive speech acts. Deconstructing these pieces is part of the analysis, so that the subtle levels of importance contained within the text may be uncovered. It highlights the tremendous significance linked with the black covering and depicts it as a powerful symbol of cohesiveness despite the many variations. The author alludes in the passage to the possibility that going to the sanctuary can offer solace and result in the abandonment of grief, stressing the transformational possibilities linked with this activity. In addition, It investigates the speaker's enhanced emotional state of melancholy when considering the recollections of the House of God. This method of self-reflection provokes thought on the ephemeral nature of human existence, giving birth to profound philosophical musings. Research elucidates the complex feelings, profound contemplations, and symbolic depth inherent in the speaker's utterances by illuminating the myriad of different parts of pragmatics in the text.

Keywords: Pragmatics, Hyperbole, Metaphorical, Assertive, Speech

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Introduction

The discipline of pragmatics analysis focuses on investigating contextual elements, discourse patterns inherent in a specific text, and the utilitarian aspects of language utilization. As Yule (1996) asserts, it is essential to consider the significance of the setting. According to Yule (1996), the communication process is influenced by socio-psychological components and contextual variables, such as the temporal and geographical dimensions in which language is formed or written. The study of pragmatics sometimes referred to simply as "pragmatics," is a branch of academia that focuses on interpreting linguistic meaning within a well-defined framework that considers both time and environment. When two individuals are having a conversation with one another, one of them will make an effort to produce a linguistic utterance that has an intentional, intended goal, while the other person will make an effort to interpret the speech and discern what the intended significance of it is supposed to be. The findings that were discovered by Brown et al. (1983) lend support to the premise that was discussed earlier in this paragraph. The degree to which the words being conveyed are understood depends on several factors, including the specificity of the message concerning its setting and the level of comprehension possessed by both the speaker and the listener. The presuppositions of knowledge held in common by the speaker and the listener are critical to successfully transmitting the message the speaker intends to convey.

Research Questions

- i. What are the key pragmatic elements, such as implicature, speech acts, and politeness strategies, present in the selected Kafi of Khawaja Ghulam Fareed?
- ii. How does Khawaja Ghulam Fareed's use of pragmatics contribute to interpreting and understanding his selected Kafi poetry?

Research Objectives

- i. To analyze the pragmatic features, such as deixis, implicature, and speech acts, within the selected Kafi of Khawaja Ghulam Fareed.
- ii. To identify how Khawaja Ghulam Fareed uses pragmatics to communicate deeper cultural and social meanings in his poetry.

Problem Statement

Although a significant amount of scholarly attention has been paid to Khawaja Ghulam Fareed's Kafi poetry, there still needs to be a noticeable gap in our all-encompassing grasp of how pragmatic components impact the interpretation of his oeuvre as well as the cultural. Although previous studies have gone into the linguistic, cultural, and historical parts of his poetry, there has yet to be a noteworthy lack of a full investigation of the pragmatic qualities of the selected Kafi. By addressing the gap mentioned earlier, this research aims to conduct an exhaustive investigation of the pragmatics present in the selected Kafi. As part of this research, we will be looking at the complex array of pragmatic choices that the poet made and the relevance of those choices in terms of how well they transmit the underlying cultural, social, and emotional nuances.

Significance of the Study

This study enriches our appreciation of the poet's writing and communication. Pragmatics and in-depth research may help. Khawaja Ghulam Fareed's Kafi pragmatics illuminate these poems' cultural and historical background because it clarifies these works' context. Because the poet penned these poems on his life. Pragmatic decisions indicate that period's social norms, values, and interpersonal dynamics. Pakistan reveres Khawaja Ghulam Fareed's poetry, notably Kafi. Kafi highly influences Pakistani music. This study preserves culture. It's vital to maintain the artist's details. This interpretation enhances this poetry's

historical and cultural context. This research explains poetry's cultural intricacies to individuals from different cultures. This research expands linguistics and communication disciplines beyond literature. Artistic expression like this reflects fundamental themes. This study illuminates pragmatic, creative communication tactics. This research helps teachers evaluate poetry's practical qualities. The research may expose this model. Regional culture, literature, language students, scholars, and hobbyists may benefit from this resource. This study on a professional poet's pragmatic methods in a historical situation may inspire contemporary poets and writers.

Literature Review

In pragmatics, [Biletzki \(1996\)](#) delineated two separate definitions, specifically intentional and extensional. To further elaborate on his viewpoint, he presented multiple pragmatics interpretations as other linguists proposed. Pragmatics can be described as the systematic study of the dynamic relationship between language and its surrounding context. Pragmatic analysis pertains to the correlation between the sign and the observer/interpreter, as delineated by [Khan & and Bughio \(2012\)](#). According to [Bates \(1976, p. 3\)](#), the concept under consideration involves the examination of "indexical rules" that create a correlation between linguistic structure and contextual factors. According to [Khan & Bughio \(2012\)](#), a connection exists between language, its core principles, and the individuals who utilize it. According to [Martín-Asensio \(2000\)](#), the proposition suggests that pragmatic analysis endeavors to build a theoretical framework that elucidates the interplay between "language structures" and the individuals who employ them. ([Haberland & Mortensen, 2016](#)) The term "it" refers to the academic discipline that systematically investigates and analyses language utilization. In her study, [Biletzki \(1996, p.457\)](#) examined different

manifestations of an extensional viewpoint, highlighting Pragmatics as the disciplinary domain focused on investigating presupposition, deixis, speech acts, implicates, and various aspects of discourse analysis ([Levinson, 1938, p. 27](#)). [Talbot \(1987\)](#) posits that the origins of the study of Pragmatics can be attributed to [Charles Morris' \(1938\)](#) exploration of the interrelationships among semiotics, syntax, and semantics. Currently, the areas mentioned earlier are categorized as psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, and neuro-linguistics, as [Uebel \(2013\)](#) argued that the investigation of a speaker's language and its corresponding significations pertains to the domain of semantics, whereas the examination of the arrangement of employed expressions constitutes a syntactic analysis. Linguists have provided multiple definitions for the field of pragmatics. [Khan & and Bughio \(2012\)](#) assert that pragmatics is a linguistic field that examines the utilization of language in authentic contexts. [Yule \(1996\)](#) posits that Pragmatics is an essential subfield within the discipline of Linguistics, serving as a bridge between language structures and the individuals that utilize them. In addition, this method makes it easier to investigate the objectives or goals of the speaker while at the same time presuming that all parties involved in the conversation have certain views, either correct or incorrect, regarding the topic at hand. According to [Yule \(1996\)](#), pragmatics is a field of study exploring the meanings that lay at the foundation of a key communication component. This is in contrast to the study of isolated sentences. According to [Abdullah \(2015\)](#), it is a widespread practice among individuals to express their well-being by using the phrase "All praise to Allah" instead of the more informal response of "I am fine." [Cruz \(2015\)](#) asserts that in 1980, linguists predominantly examined pragmatics, a field concerned with analyzing meaning and its contextual ramifications. Multiple levels of

relevance can be explored to delve into different layers of meaning. The author has classified the three stages as abstract semantics, contextual semantics, and illocutionary force. The discovery of abstract meaning can be facilitated through dictionaries or other relevant reference materials. On the other hand, the concept of force relates to the speaker's aim. Each of the three tiers involves analyzing the semantic aspects of phrases, clauses, and entire sentences. Pragmatics pertains to examining how the surrounding context influences interpreting meaning. The text exhibits several instances of pragmatic devices.

Research Methodology

The research methodology refers to the systematic approach and techniques employed in conducting a study or investigation. It encompasses the overall design and data collection. The present research employs a qualitative approach. A kafi has been chosen for a pragmatics study, specifically from the English-translated book containing the Kafies of Khawaja Ghulam Fareed. Kafi No. 15 was chosen via purposive sampling due to its higher concentration of pragmatics features compared to other Kafies. Pragmatics analysis has been undertaken within the framework of several theories of pragmatics put out by researchers and linguists.

Theoretical Framework

Language may cause actions, according to [J.L. Austin](#) and [John Searle's](#) Speech Act theory. The categorization system classifies speech actions as aggressive, directive, commissive, expressive, and declarative. The framework emphasizes speech actions' illocutionary force and their meaning beyond literal interpretation ([Searle, 1969](#)). Paul Grice's Cooperative Principle and Conversational Maxims Theory are major pragmatics frameworks. The Cooperative Principle requires honest, relevant, and cooperative communication. The Maxim of

Quantity emphasizes delivering adequate information; the Maxim of Quality emphasizes honesty. Relation highlights relevance, and Manner emphasizes clarity and organization. Understanding conversational implicatures and indirect meaning requires Grice's paradigm ([Allott, 2005](#)). This theoretical framework indicates speakers want to participate. This study examines how individuals sustain strong social connections while managing hurdles to the recipient's positive and negative face, which affects acceptance and independence. This concept illuminates cultural and contextual politeness, says [Goldsmith \(2007\)](#). In contextual pragmatics, context matters for comprehending statements. Language is primarily indexical; thus, context determines words and sentences. Howard Giles' Speech Accommodation hypothesis examines how individuals adapt to their conversation partners. This study examines how language expresses group membership, social cohesion, politeness, and other qualities. This idea applies to intercultural and intergroup language usage ([Giles et al., 1987](#)).

Text: "My charming beloved is bidding me farewell today."

Pragmatic analysis

Politeness

The speaker decided to use the phrase "bidding me farewell," which gives the impression that they are treating the listener with respect and courtesy. This may involve accepting the person's desire to leave, or it may relate to a strategy for decreasing the impact of the negative conditions on the individual. Either way, it is important to take this step.

Emotional tone

The phrase "bidding me farewell today" has an emotional tone, indicating that the speaker may be experiencing grief, nostalgia, or a mixture of these emotions in response to the departure of their lover. This is likely because the term is typically employed when

parting with someone. The word "beloved" lends a more sincere tone to the statement because it is included.

Conversational implicature

When further details are supplied, the reason for the leave may be comprehended and appreciated in their entirety. There is a broad variety of reasons for the departure, ranging from a short trip to another location to an extended period without touching the person. Because there is a need for more specific information, each audience member is at liberty to draw their inferences or formulate their hypotheses on the circumstance.

Speech acts

There are two possible interpretations of the statement: either it is an expression of the speaker's sentiments or a disclosure of the existing conditions to someone else. The statement might be interpreted in any of these two ways. Through this, it may be possible for their sentiments over the departure to be expressed to the listener or a third party.

Coherence with cultural norms

A farewell can have several different meanings and practices attached to it, depending on the culture in which it is said. To properly grasp what the speaker is trying to convey, it is necessary to consider that people from different cultures have different ideas about what constitutes a proper farewell.

Text: "I have taken the burden of suffering on my head."

Pragmatics Devices

There are a few pragmatic devices to be found in the sentence that reads, "The sacred and supreme House of God is free from all imperfections." Pragmatic devices are language components used to fulfill a particular communicative function or purpose. Here are two different pragmatic devices that could be used in this text.

Assertive speech act

It is possible to interpret the statement "The sacred and supreme House of God is free from all imperfections" as an act of aggressive speech. It is asserting something concerning the holy Temple of God or proclaiming a fact about it. This assertion is being made by the speaker, who is presenting it to the audience as a fact that they have reason to believe is accurate. The information and a certain point of view are communicated through the utilization of this pragmatic instrument.

Hyperbole

This is an example of the figure of speech known as hyperbole, which consists of making excessive or exaggerated claims. Exaggeration can be seen in how the phrase "free from all imperfections" is phrased. The speaker exaggerates the holiness and purity of the House of God by emphasizing that there is not even a single defect to be found in the building. This emphasizes that only one flaw can be found in the structure. This is done to emphasize that the structure is flawless in every respect and hammer the argument home. I hope that demonstrating this makes it abundantly clear that the temple is faultless. The speaker uses this logical strategy to establish emphasis, generate a significant emotional response, or demonstrate reverence for the House of God.

Pragmatic analysis

The audience should interpret the statements made by the speaker as suggesting that the individual in question has cheerfully accepted or wholeheartedly embraced the burden of their suffering. This remark might be intended to demonstrate a sense of strength or resiliency in the face of obstacles by expressing a sense of personal responsibility and devotion to one's goals.

Text: "The sacred and supreme House of God is free from all imperfections."

Pragmatics Devices

Declarative speech act

It is possible to interpret the statement "The sacred and supreme House of God is free from all imperfections" as a kind of declarative speech; nevertheless, this interpretation is not the only one that is valid. This verse makes a factual statement concerning the location of the dwelling place of God by using other biblical passages. The person speaking claims that this is a fact that is generally known, or the vast majority of people recognize that. The speaker intends to distribute knowledge and communicate their perspective on the nature of the House of God by using a specific kind of speech known as a declarative statement.

Emphatic language

The use of harsh language, such as the adjectives "sacred" and "supreme," as well as the phrase "free from all imperfections," are instances of this phenomenon. The employment of these language elements provides emphasis and intensity to the statement, calling attention to the unique traits held by the House of God and contributing to the overall purpose of the statement. Strong convictions may be conveyed to readers and listeners through emphatic language, which likewise has a more significant impression on whoever is doing the receiving.

Pragmatic analysis

The speaker emphasizes the divine holiness of the location by describing the House of God as a setting that is completely free of any flaws whatsoever. This comment expresses the regard and belief held by the speaker for the perfect and holy nature of the religious location they are referring to.

Text: "Here, God's bondsmen of higher and lower ranks become recipients in consonance with their asking."

A few pragmatic techniques in the text read, "Here, God's bondsmen of higher and lower ranks become recipients in consonance with their asking." Pragmatic devices are language elements that fulfill a particular

communicative function or purpose. Pragmatic devices are also known as pragma. The following are two potential pragmatic devices that are used in this book.

Descriptive speech act

The statement that "God's bondsmen of higher and lower ranks become recipients in consonance with their asking" might be seen as a speaking act that describes what happens. It explains how people, sometimes referred to as "God's bondsmen," receive what they ask for based on their prayers. This method of pragmatism provides information and explanation regarding a specific facet of the scenario that is being described.

Metaphorical language

The phrase "God's bondsmen of higher and lower ranks" uses figurative language. It is a metaphor that alludes to those devoted to God, highlighting the many levels of spiritual accomplishment or dedication each individual possesses. Language that makes use of metaphors communicates abstract ideas by drawing similarities to aspects that are more concrete or are better known.

Pragmatic analysis

The speaker seems to be implying that those who worship God, regardless of their socioeconomic standing, would receive what they ask for depending on the ambitions they have. This remark provides the impression that the author believes in heavenly favor or advantages for those who worship God devoutly and seek him for fulfillment. This interpretation of the author's beliefs is supported by the assertion that the author believes in the presence of heaven.

**Text: "I laud the peace of Divine Majesty.
I laud the sacred sanctuary of Allah.
I laud the venerable House of Allah.
It is the treasury of blessings."**

Expressive language

The phrase "God's bondsmen of higher and lower ranks" uses figurative language. It is a metaphor that alludes to those devoted to God, highlighting the many levels of

spiritual accomplishment or dedication each individual possesses. Language that makes use of metaphors communicates abstract ideas by drawing similarities to aspects that are more concrete or are better known.

Pragmatic analysis

The use of the verb "laud," as well as the adjectives "peace," "sacred and "venerable," creates a tone that is emotive and reverent. The speaker pays homage to Divine Majesty, the sanctuary of Allah, and the House of Allah, expressing appreciation, praise, and regard for these three entities. Expressive language is used to transmit feelings and produce a particular effect on the reader or the listener.

Hyperbole

The phrase 'It is the treasure of blessings' is an illustrative instance of hyperbole, a rhetorical device characterized by exaggerated or extravagant claims. The phrase "It is the treasury of blessings" exemplifies the use of hyperbole. The speaker employed the rhetorical device of exaggeration to emphasize the profound value of the benefits linked with the House of Allah. This was achieved by characterizing it as a "treasury of blessings," a hyperbolic expression that metaphorically conveys the abundance and richness of these gifts. This pragmatic approach aims to cultivate concentration, elicit a deep emotional response, and direct awareness towards the sanctity of the House of Allah.

Metaphorical language

The statement "It is the treasury of blessings" uses metaphorical language to portray the House of Allah as a repository or storehouse of blessings. This imagery emphasizes the abundance of blessings found within the religious site.

Pragmatic analysis

The speaker expresses admiration and praise for the peaceful nature associated with the divine power, the sacred sanctuary of Allah, and the esteemed House of Allah. This

statement reflects the speaker's deep reverence for the divine and their belief in the abundant blessings that can be obtained through worship.

Text: "Undoubtedly, the seeker of peace, who enters the compound of the sanctuary, becomes free from sorrow."

Assertive speech act

Consider the claim that "Undoubtedly, the seeker of peace, who enters the compound of the sanctuary, becomes free from sorrow." One approach to look at the assertion that "Undoubtedly, the seeker of peace, who enters the compound of the sanctuary, becomes free from sorrow" is as a speech act of assertiveness is to look at it as a statement. Either a statement about the effect of entering the sanctuary's grounds is made, or a fact about that effect is presented, depending on the nature of the passage. The individual yearning for peace will be released from their grief upon entering; as the speaker emphasizes, expressing confidence in the conclusion is the speaker's way of expressing their conviction in the outcome. The purpose of this method, which is both informative and argumentative, is to show a certain point of view while simultaneously delivering information.

Causal relationship

The phrase "the seeker of peace, who enters the compound of the sanctuary, becomes free from sorrow" gives the impression of a causal connection between the two events. It gives the impression that stepping foot inside the sanctuary's walls will ultimately result in the weariness of life being lifted. This pragmatic approach establishes a cause-and-effect relationship between the action of entering and the resultant freedom from sadness, stressing the sanctuary's transforming potential. The liberation from sorrow is the result of entering the sanctuary. Its purpose is to illuminate the motivations or outcomes that led to a given circumstance.

Pragmatic analysis

Those looking for peace are told by the speaker that entering the sanctuary compound (the speaker seems to be referring to the House of God) will bring them deliverance from their sorrows. This remark suggests a belief in the emotional and spiritual consolation that can be found within the sanctuary of a religious building.

Text: "My sense of primordial sorrow has heightened by remembering the compound of the House of God."

Personal experience and emotion

The words in the book convey the feelings and experiences that the speaker had personally. It is clear from the term "my sense of primordial sorrow" that the speaker is experiencing significant melancholy. It gives the impression that the speaker has a deep emotional connection to the topic.

Cause-effect relationship

According to the statement, recalling the structure of the House of God is connected to an intensified feeling of primeval melancholy. This suggests a connection between the two that can be understood in terms of cause and effect. It provides the idea that remembering has reignited or magnified the speaker's previously existing feelings of regret, which is a misleading but plausible interpretation of the situation.

Descriptive language

The evolution of the statement into a piece of descriptive writing is helped by inserting the term "primordial sorrow" into the sentence. It brings forth an overwhelming sense of sadness, which gives the impression that the suffering the speaker is going through will last for a very long time and is of great severity. The material that was given contains examples of certain pragmatic devices that may be found there. Pragmatic devices are linguistic components that serve a certain communication purpose or aim, also known as pragmatism. The term "pragma" can also refer to pragmatic devices. The two

instances that follow are possible examples of pragmatic devices utilized in this book.

Evidentially

The phrase "by remembering the compound of the House of God" implies that some evidentiary device is involved. The speaker insinuates that the person's current emotional condition is due to their remembrance or memory of the complex that houses the House of God when they say that "by remembering," their sadness has been "heightened." The speaker's subjective experience is communicated through this pragmatic device, which also serves as a foundation for the speaker's emotional state.

Text: "My heart prompts me to take bane for (mere) life is false and meaningless."

Pragmatics Devices

Evaluative statement

The statement that "for (mere) life is false and meaningless" has the potential to be construed as a value judgment due to the implication that it carries with it. It concludes or makes a judgment on the core of existence, stating that it is a falsehood and that it is without importance. The speaker offers their viewpoint on how they feel their life lacks meaning and purpose due to the circumstances they are now facing. This pragmatic approach serves as a medium via which they may communicate their evaluation or viewpoint.

Personal reflection and introspection

The text reveals the speaker's thoughts and contemplation. The phrase "My heart prompts me" indicates that the speaker listens to their inner emotions and desires.

Contrast and comparison

The phrase "to take bane" contrasts with the notion of life being false and meaningless. It suggests that the speaker is willing to embrace hardship or adversity instead of accepting a life they deem useless.

Pragmatic analysis

It is conceivable that the speaker's emotions, or their deepest thoughts, are

urging them to endure in the face of misfortune as a reaction to the notion that life in this world is transient and devoid of any permanent value. If this is the case, the speaker's words should be taken with a grain of salt. This comment conveys the message that one needs to disregard the transient nature of one's life in this world and, as an alternative, gives significance to spiritual or enduring qualities.

Text: "Now, I am turning the reins toward my native town (returning)."

Temporal reference

The word "now" indicates that turning the reins is happening now. It establishes a specific timeframe for the event being described.

Self-disclosure

The statement provides insight into the intention or behavior of the speaker. The speaker reveals their choice or plans to head back toward their hometown by saying, "I am turning the reins," which is an action phrase.

Metaphorical language

The metaphor of "turning the reins" expresses how the speaker has changed their path or direction in what they are saying. It gives the impression that the person speaking is assuming power or returning to their hometown.

Spatial reference

The mention of the "native town" specifies the destination or target of the speaker's journey. It provides a specific location and adds context to the statement.

Pragmatic analysis

The speaker indicates they are going differently and will return to where they grew up. This remark gives the impression of a journey or movement, which may indicate a yearning to return to one's roots.

Text: "My heart has cultivated true ties of love. My God! Make me revisit the place."

Self-disclosure and personal reflection

Based on what is said, the reader can make assumptions about the speaker's

sentiments and experiences. The phrase "My heart has cultivated true ties of love" suggests that the speaker's heart has established genuine and significant relationships with the individuals in their immediate environment.

Direct address and invocation

The phrase "My God!" serves as a direct address to a divine entity. It expresses the speaker's invocation or plea to God for a specific request or desire.

Request or wish

The statement "Make me revisit the place" expresses the speaker's desire or wish to revisit a particular location. It signifies the speaker's longing to return to that place.

Pragmatic purpose

The statement accomplishes conveying the speaker's feelings, calling upon a supernatural being, and expressing a wish to visit a certain location again. The speaker may be trying to communicate their desire for emotional bonds and their faith that supernatural intervention would grant them their request.

Text: "My heart is desirous of my beloved."

It does not find breathing space in the house, city, or lane."

Personal emotion and desire

The text expresses the speaker's emotions and desires. The phrase "My heart is desirous of my beloved" conveys the speaker's strong longing or yearning for someone they hold dear.

Metaphorical language

The expression "My heart does not find breathing space" is a metaphor to convey the passion with which the speaker desires something. It emphasizes how deeply the speaker yearns for something else since it gives the impression that the speaker's heart is being confined or smothered in the speaker's current circumstances.

Spatial reference

The mention of "the house, city, or lane" provides specific locations to illustrate the extent of the speaker's feelings. It suggests that the speaker's desire is not limited to a particular physical space but encompasses their entire environment.

Pragmatic analysis

The speaker conveys a great longing for the person they hold dear. They allude to the fact that familiar environments, such as the house, the city, or the lane, make them feel as though their hearts are being smothered or constricted. This phrase communicates the speaker's strong yearning and the impression that their surroundings trap them.

"I will again realize the strokes of circumambulation in case fortune smiles on me."

Conditional statement

The phrase "in case fortune smiles on me" introduces a condition or a hypothetical scenario. It gives the impression that the ability of the speaker to "realize the strokes of circumambulation" is dependent on the intervention of fate or luck in a positive way.

Future intention or plan

The statement "I will again realize the strokes of circumambulation" expresses the speaker's intention or plan for the future. It indicates their desire to engage in the act of circumambulation again.

Verbal commitment

The phrase "again" gives the impression that the speaker has already completed the circumambulation strokes at some point. It gives the impression of a commitment or a willingness to carry out the activity again soon.

Speech acts

Analyze how Khawaja Ghulam Fareed employs speech acts in his poetry. Look for instances where he expresses emotions, requests conveys advice, or states opinions. Consider the intended effects and communicative purposes of these speech

acts within the context of his mystical and philosophical themes.

Deixis and reference

Examine how Fareed's poetry uses deixis and reference to establish the time, space, and participants. Identify instances of pronouns, demonstratives, or other referential expressions and analyze how they contribute to the overall meaning and effect of the poetry.

Metaphorical language

Explore the metaphorical language used by Fareed to convey mystical and philosophical concepts. Analyze how he employs metaphors, similes, and other figurative language to communicate abstract ideas, evoke emotions, and create vivid imagery for the reader.

Pragmatic presuppositions

Find the locations where Fareed communicates meaning depending on pragmatic presuppositions, and underline those places when you find them. Understanding a certain assertion calls for using specific presuppositions, which may also be referred to as assumptions or background beliefs. Consider the idea that the reader may only grasp the deeper meanings in Fareed's poetry if they had some prior exposure to a certain religion or cultural tradition.

Cultural and social context: Think about the cultural and social setting in which Fareed was operating when he penned his poetry. Examine how the norms, values, and beliefs of his period and place may have impacted his use of pragmatic methods.

Conclusion

The pragmatics analysis of Khawaja Ghulam Fareed's Kafi poetry shows that the poet uses various pragmatic elements to convey significant concepts and sentiments. The poetry contains arguments, directives, commissives, expressives, and statements. These speaking actions show the poet's communicative goals beyond the lines' literal

meanings. Khawaja Ghulam Fareed's HisKafi uses conversational implicatures to convey several meanings and spark thinking. Understanding the poet's link with the Sufi tradition and the poems' intended meanings depends on the poetry's setting. The Kafi shows the poet's desire for social harmony and respect in his interactions with varied audiences. These approaches reveal the poet's awareness of societal norms and values in his time and place. The relevance theory shows how Khawaja Ghulam Fareed's Kafi poet masters relevance, making each phrase meaningful in the context of love, spirituality, and mysticism. Comparing Khawaja Ghulam Fareed's poetry to other Sufi poets shows similarities and differences in pragmatics. A pragmatics analysis of Khawaja Ghulam Fareed's Kafi shows the poet's linguistic innovation and ability to use pragmatics to convey meaning and evoke emotion. Kafi poetry exhibits spiritual devotion and reveals Sufi culture and language. This research illuminates traditional Sufi poetry's practical roots and continued relevance to literary studies. Pragmatics study on Sufi literature may help us grasp these timeless works' complex language, culture, and spirituality.

Recommendations

Research in Context

Carry out exhaustive research into the historical, cultural, and social milieu in which each Kafi was written. This will help in grasping the significance of the poet's words and analyzing the pragmatic choices that were made. Notations and highlighting are included. Annotate the Kafi text to locate and emphasize the various pragmatic aspects that are there. Different sorts of pragmatic qualities, such as direct speech acts, indirect speech acts, implicatures, and so on, can be distinguished from one another with the help of symbols or color-coding.

Corpus Linguistics Tools

Make use of the tools provided by corpus linguistics to measure and investigate the frequency and distribution of particular pragmatic features throughout the chosen Kafi. This may provide quantitative insights that can support the qualitative analysis you have been doing.

Cultural Sensitivity

Approach the analysis with cultural sensitivity, considering that certain pragmatic choices may have deeper cultural meanings. Observe that certain cultural norms may differ from country to country.

Case Studies

Select particular Kafi to act as examples in the case studies. Please provide in-depth analyses of these situations, focusing on how pragmatics relates to the poetry's interpretation, emotional impact, and cultural resonance.

Visual Aids

To provide a graphical representation of your findings, you should use visual aids such as tables, graphs, and charts. This helps the reader understand the significance of the various pragmatic parts and their distribution.

Interdisciplinary Connections

When quoting from or transcribing material from the Kafi, observe all applicable copyright and intellectual property laws. Attribute translations accurately and ensure you have permission before using them, if necessary.

References

- Abdullah, M. (2015). *Deixis: A Pragmatics Analysis*. *Language in India*, 15(12), 3–9.
- Allott, N. (2005). *Paul Grice, reasoning and pragmatics*. *UCL Working Papers in Linguistics*, pp. 17, 217–243.
- Biletzki, A. (1996). *Is there a history of pragmatics?* *Journal of Pragmatics*, 25(4), 455–470.
- Brown, G., Brown, G. D., Yule, G., Brown, G. R., & Gillian, B. (1983). *Discourse analysis*. Cambridge University Press.

- Giles, H., Mulac, A., Bradac, J. J., & Johnson, P. (1987). Speech accommodation theory: The first decade and beyond. *Annals of the International Communication Association*, 10(1), 13-48.
- Goldsmith, D. J. (2007). Brown and Levinson's politeness theory. *Explaining communication: Contemporary theories and exemplars*, pp. 219–236.
- Haberland, H., & Mortensen, J. (2016). Transcription as second-order entextualization: The challenge of heteroglossia. *Interdisciplinary studies in pragmatics, culture, and society*, 581-600.
- Khan, Q., & Bughio, F. A. (2012). Nunnery scene: A pragmatic analysis of Hamlet-Ophelia encounter. *3L, Language, Linguistics, Literature*, 18(2).
- Martín-Asensio, G. (2000). *Transitivity-based Foregrounding in the Acts of the Apostles: A Functional-grammatical Approach to the Lukan Perspective (Vol. 8)*. A&C Black.
- Searle, J. R. (1969). *Speech acts: An essay in the philosophy of language (Vol. 626)*. Cambridge University Press.
- Yule, G. (1996). *Pragmatics*. Oxford University Press.